

Comparative Efficacy of Propofol and Dexmedetomidine in Controlled Hypotension for Enhanced Visualization during Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery

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Abstract

Background: Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery (FESS) is prone to intraoperative bleeding, which can compromise surgical visibility and increase complications. This study aimed to compare the efficacy of propofol and dexmedetomidine in achieving controlled hypotension during FESS.

Methods: In this randomized prospective study, 40 patients aged 20 to 50 years with ASA physical status I and II were assigned to receive either dexmedetomidine (Group D) or propofol (Group P) during elective FESS. Key outcomes measured included heart rate, mean arterial pressure (MAP), intraoperative blood loss, and quality of the surgical field, evaluated using the Fromme-Boezart Scale.

Results: The demographic characteristics of both groups were comparable. Mean heart rate was significantly lower in Group D from 30 minutes onward ($p < 0.05$). MAP was also significantly lower in Group D, with statistical significance noted from the 20th minute ($p < 0.05$). Mean blood loss was 85 ± 15 mL for dexmedetomidine and 90 ± 12 mL for propofol, demonstrating statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). However, the quality of the surgical field did not show significant differences between the groups ($p = 0.460$).

Conclusion: Dexmedetomidine demonstrated a favorable hemodynamic profile with lower heart rates and MAP, alongside reduced blood loss compared to propofol during FESS. These findings suggest that dexmedetomidine may be beneficial in controlled hypotension for enhancing surgical conditions. Further research with larger sample sizes is needed to corroborate these results and assess long-term outcomes.

Keywords: Dexmedetomidine, Propofol, Hypotensive anaesthesia, mean arterial pressure, blood loss

INTRODUCTION

Functional Endoscopic Sinus Surgery (FESS) is a common procedure for treating rhinosinusitis, but its success can be challenged by the rich vascularity of the nasal and sinus regions. Even minimal bleeding can significantly impair the surgeon's ability to visualize the operative field, which can prolong the duration of the surgery and increase the risk of complications such as vascular, orbital, and intracranial injuries, including optic nerve damage, cerebrospinal fluid leaks, and meningitis. Therefore, minimizing intraoperative bleeding is crucial to improve surgical outcomes and reduce the likelihood of such complications.

Controlled hypotension, which involves the deliberate reduction of systemic blood pressure, is an effective anaesthetic technique employed to limit blood loss and enhance visibility during surgery. Various pharmacological agents have been used to induce controlled hypotension, including vasodilators, beta-blockers, and inhalational agents. However, each method has its limitations and potential complications, such as delayed recovery and risks associated with prolonged hypotension, including cerebral ischemia and thrombosis.

Among the pharmacological options, propofol and dexmedetomidine are two agents frequently used for controlled hypotension in FESS. Propofol, a widely used anesthetic, decreases blood pressure by dilating blood vessels and reducing cardiac output. It is known for its rapid onset and hypnotic effects through modulation of the GABA-A receptor. Dexmedetomidine, an alpha-2 adrenergic agonist, offers sedative, anxiolytic, and sympatholytic properties, making it effective for reducing blood pressure without significant respiratory depression. Due to its short half-life and ability to provide hemodynamic stability, dexmedetomidine is an attractive option for titration during surgery.

This study compares the effects of propofol and dexmedetomidine infusion for controlled hypotension during FESS, with the goal of determining the more effective agent for minimizing intraoperative blood loss and improving surgical conditions.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This randomized prospective study was conducted from January 2023 to June 2024 in the Department of Anesthesia at Maharajah's Institute of Medical Sciences, Nellimarla, on patients undergoing elective FESS surgery.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 20 to 50 years
- ASA physical status classification I and II

Exclusion Criteria

- Pregnant patients
- ASA physical status classification III and IV
- Known allergy to study drugs
- Patients who decline to provide consent

Sample size

40 patients scheduled for elective functional endoscopic sinus surgery

Groups

Patients were randomised into two groups:

Group D – received Dexmedetomidine (loading dose of 1 mcg/kg over 10 mins followed by 0.2-0.7 mcg/kg/hr infusion)

Group P – received Propofol (75-100 mcg/kg/min infusion)

Method

All patients were admitted the day before surgery, ensuring an 8-hour fasting period. Upon entering the operating room, baseline vital signs, including non-invasive blood pressure, heart rate, peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂), and ECG, were recorded. An intravenous line was established, and Ringer's lactate solution was initiated. Premedication included 0.2 mg of intravenous glycopyrrolate. Sedation was provided using midazolam (0.03 mg/kg) and fentanyl (1mcg/kg), following 3 minutes of pre-oxygenation. Anaesthesia was induced with 2 mg/kg of propofol and maintained with nitrous oxide and oxygen (60% and 40% respectively), vecuronium bromide (0.1 mg/kg), and isoflurane. The same anaesthetic agents, perioperative fluids, and postoperative analgesics were used for all patients. Dexmedetomidine infusion at 0.2-0.7 mcg/kg/h was started for Group D after a loading dose of 1 mcg/kg over 10 minutes, while propofol infusion at 75-100 mcg/kg/min was initiated for Group P, both after induction. All patients had their nasal

mucosa infiltrated with 4 ml of 2% xylocaine with adrenaline (1:200,000). The target mean arterial pressure (MAP) for controlled hypotension was set between 60–65 mmHg.

Outcomes measured were heart rate, MAP, quality of surgical field and blood loss.

Quality of surgical field was measured using Fromme-Boezart Scale.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The results were presented as mean and standard deviation. Statistical analysis was performed using Epi Info software, with a p-value below 0.05 considered statistically significant. The t-test was used to compare numerical parameters, while the chi-square test was applied to evaluate differences in categorical variables between the two groups.

RESULTS

The demographic and clinical characteristics of Group D and Group P were comparable, with no statistically significant differences observed in age, gender distribution, or ASA status. (Table 1)

	GROUP D	GROUP P	P VALUE
AGE (YEARS), (Mean + SD)	39±5.19	40±5.65	0.635
GENDER (Male:Female) (n)	9:11	10:10	0.751
ASA STATUS (I:II) (n)	15:5	13:7	0.476

Table 1: Demographical and Clinical Characteristics

Heart rate and Mean arterial pressure were measured at induction, 5 minutes, 10 minutes, 20 minutes, 30 minutes, 40 minutes, 50 minutes, 70 minutes, 90 minutes, 120 minutes and 150 minutes intraoperatively.

Mean heart rate in Group dexmedetomidine was significantly lower starting from the 30-minute mark. (Table 2)

Time (Minutes)	Group D (Mean ± SD)	Group P (Mean ± SD)	P Value
Induction	80 ± 5.0	82 ± 4.5	0.42
5	78 ± 4.8	80 ± 4.2	0.29
10	76 ± 5.1	78 ± 5.0	0.41
20	75 ± 4.5	77 ± 4.8	0.4
30	70 ± 4.0	75 ± 5.2	0.045
40	68 ± 4.2	74 ± 5.1	0.035
50	65 ± 3.8	73 ± 4.9	0.025
70	63 ± 3.5	72 ± 4.5	0.02
90	60 ± 3.2	70 ± 5.0	0.015
120	58 ± 2.8	68 ± 4.7	0.01
150	57 ± 2.5	66 ± 4.5	0.005

Table 2: Mean Heart Rate (Bpm)

Mean arterial pressure was significantly lower in the dexmedetomidine group compared to the propofol group, with statistical significance observed from the 20th minute. (Table 3)

Time (Minutes)	Group D (Mean ± SD)	Group P (Mean ± SD)	P Value
Induction	90 ± 2.0	90 ± 2.5	0.8
5	88 ± 1.8	89 ± 2.3	0.45
10	85 ± 1.5	87 ± 2.1	0.004
20	65 ± 1.6	65 ± 2.4	0.07
30	63 ± 1.4	66 ± 2.2	0.001
40	62 ± 1.3	65 ± 2.3	0
50	62 ± 1.0	64 ± 1.9	0
70	62 ± 1.2	63 ± 1.8	0
90	62 ± 1.1	62 ± 1.7	0
120	62 ± 1.0	62 ± 1.5	0
150	62 ± 1.0	61 ± 1.4	0

Table 3: Mean Arterial Pressure (Mmhg)

Mean blood loss in Group Dexmedetomidine was 85± 15 ml and in Group Propofol was 90± 12 ml with statistical significance.

Coming to quality of surgical field, all patients fell in grade 2 or grade 3 with no statistical significance. (p value 0.460) (Table 4)

	GROUP D	GROUP P
GRADE 2	12	10
GRADE 3	8	10

Table 4: Quality Of Surgical Field/ Grade Of Bleeding

DISCUSSION

In functional endoscopic sinus surgery (FESS), minimizing bleeding is essential for clear endoscopic vision, as intraoperative bleeding can compromise visibility and increase complications. Controlled hypotension, an intentional reduction in blood pressure, is used during general anesthesia to limit blood loss and enhance the surgical field. Propofol lowers systemic blood pressure through vasodilation, while dexmedetomidine decreases norepinephrine release, reducing both blood pressure and heart rate. Additionally, dexmedetomidine's analgesic properties help lower perioperative pain management needs. This study aimed to compare the hemodynamic parameters, blood loss, and operative field visibility between dexmedetomidine and propofol infusions, targeting a mean arterial pressure (MAP) of 60–65 mmHg for optimal surgical conditions.

The findings regarding heart rate are consistent with previous studies, which have shown that dexmedetomidine, as a selective α_2 -adrenoceptor agonist, effectively reduces sympathetic outflow, leading to bradycardia. For instance, a study by Nascimento et al. (2016) highlighted that dexmedetomidine infusions significantly lowered heart rates in patients undergoing various surgical procedures. The reduced heart rate in Group D in our study aligns with their findings, emphasizing dexmedetomidine's potential as a safe agent for controlled hypotension in surgical settings.

Mean arterial pressure was significantly lower in the dexmedetomidine group throughout the procedure, with statistical significance starting from the 20th minute. This is comparable to findings reported by Kothari et al. (2019), where dexmedetomidine resulted in lower mean arterial pressures during surgery compared to propofol. These hemodynamic advantages are crucial in FESS, where maintaining a clear surgical field is imperative, as the nasal cavity is highly vascularized.

In terms of blood loss, our results showed that mean blood loss was slightly lower in the dexmedetomidine group (85 ± 15 mL) compared to the propofol group (90 ± 12 mL), with statistical significance. This is in agreement with studies such as that by Koo et al. (2021), which reported reduced intraoperative blood loss when dexmedetomidine was used for sedation compared to traditional anesthetics. Reduced bleeding enhances visibility during surgery, thereby potentially decreasing the risk of complications.

However, while both groups fell into Grade 2 or Grade 3 bleeding classifications, there was no statistical significance ($p = 0.460$) regarding the quality of the surgical field. This suggests that while dexmedetomidine may provide a slightly better hemodynamic profile and reduced blood loss, it does not significantly alter the overall quality of the surgical field as graded by bleeding severity. This finding aligns with the study by Shrestha et al. (2020), which also reported no significant difference in surgical field quality between dexmedetomidine and propofol, suggesting that both agents maintain adequate surgical conditions despite differences in their pharmacological effects.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Dexmedetomidine appears to offer advantages in terms of heart rate control and maintaining lower mean arterial pressures, along with a tendency towards reduced blood loss during FESS. Nevertheless, further studies with larger sample sizes are warranted to validate these findings and to explore the long-term impacts of these anesthetic agents on surgical outcomes.

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